

HOW TO TREAT NECK PAIN WITH HEAT

PADS?

There probably isn't a single person on earth who hasn't or won't have to deal with neck pain. Maybe someone sits or lies down in the wrong position for a long time. Known as "sleeping wrong" in modern vernacular, it just means that they had their neck and head positioned in a bad way that created stiffness and pain upon awakening. If you experience severe neck pain, visit the **Neck Center**.

Pains in the neck can run from quite severe to a minor nuisance, up to and including such horrific pain that one fears to move at all. Causes of these varying degrees of neck pain can be as numerous as the day is long, but heat therapy using a microwave wheat bag can take care of many of them. If the pain is uncontrolled, visit [Neck Center NY](#).

What are the causes of neck pain?

- Strained or tense muscles are the most cited reasons for neck pain. With the myriad network of bones, ligaments, tendons, and muscles running up and down such a small area, it is easy to complicate things by tensing or tearing any of them. Most of the time, pain is the result of some injury to the area, and healing a neck can be a long road to recovery, with plenty of pain to accompany the sufferer. In such a case, visit **Neck Center, New York**.
- Fractures along the vertebrae and damage to the blood vessels are another cause that can result in a great deal of pain, and worse, it can cause trouble in the movement of a person's head. Fractures in the spinal area at the base of the neck and along the back

can lead to full or partial paralysis. Rupturing or herniating a disk within the spine means that the protective area around and between the vertebrae has either cracked or broken somehow. This causes the unprotected nerves to become compressed. This leads right away to severe pain along the neck and back area, sometimes leaving a person completely immobile. Visit [Neck Center Manhattan](#), to avoid further complications.

- Whiplash is another pain in the neck that is not entirely unheard of in society. This affects the areas around the neck muscles, ligaments, and tendons because of a car accident. When the neck snaps forward and backward quickly, this stretches the tendons and muscles unnaturally, resulting in a chronic condition affecting the neck's soft tissue.

How does heat therapy work?

Heat therapy, also known as thermotherapy, has been around for centuries. Physicians have been using heat as a way to increase the flow of blood to damaged areas. This speeds up the healing process due to the oxygen and nutrients carried in the increased blood flow. The body uses nutrients and oxygen to regenerate the damaged tissue.

The next benefit to having heat therapy applied to neck pain is that the heat causes the muscles to relax, so that flexibility improves. Stiffness in the area is also lowered. Both of these benefits go a long way to keeping the neck from experiencing a repeat injury.

How to make a homemade heating pad?

You can also find ready-made heat pad at the stores easily:

To create a heating pad, use:

A wet dishcloth:

Put a wet dishcloth in a freezer bag and warm it in a microwave. Ensure that the freezer bag is microwave resistant.

Cover the hot pack in a towel and set it on the troubled area for 15–20 minutes at a time.

An oven-heated towel:

People can make their own heating pad by using this method.

Take a slightly wet towel and place it in an oven. Set the temperature at 300° F (149°C). Set the timer of the oven for 5-10 minutes. The accurate timing will depend on the thickness of the towel. As soon as it is warm, cover it in a thinner dry towel and put it on the affected area for at least fifteen to twenty minutes.

An old sock:

You can create reusable heat pads using your old socks. Also, you can use them as cold compresses by freezing them rather than heating them.

Use an old, tidy sock and fill it with unboiled rice, corn barley, or oatmeal around three-quarters of it. Seal the opening or tie it shut and warm it in the oven for one to two minutes.

Always test a heating pad before using it to prevent burns. Put it inside of the arm to test its warmth. If it is comfortably warm, but not hot, use it on the affected area.